

**SOCIO – ECONOMIC AND CULTURAL DETERMINANTS OF GIRL-CHILD EDUCATION
IN INDIA**

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Abstract

Women education is an essential need to change their status in the society. Educated women can play a very important role in the society for socio-economic development. Education eliminates inequalities and disparities as the means of recovering their status within and out of their families. It is the key factor for women empowerment, prosperity, development and welfare. Education provides more strength to women. Such strength comes from the process of empowerment and empowerment will come from the education. Education plays a significant role in women empowerment inequality and vulnerability of women in the society in India. This paper is an effort to capture the emerging picture with respect to women's education in India.

The main purpose of this research paper is to understand the factors that affect the girl child education. Improvement in the education and literacy skills of the girls are primarily based upon factors such as, socio-economic, socio-cultural, educational levels of the parents and distance from school. These factors affect the participation of girls in schools and in enhancing their educational skills and abilities. There are number of social, economic, familial, cultural and educational issues that prove to be impediments within the course of acquisition of education by the girls and compel them to drop out. The main areas that have been taken into account in this research paper are, deprivation of the girl child education, factors affecting female participation in education, factors leading to drop out of girls from schools, factors affecting the completion of education by girls, child labour, child abuse, child marriage, female foeticide and female infanticide, and measures to promote girl child education.

Keywords: Women education, empowerment, opportunities, foeticide, infanticide

Introduction

Education in its general sense is a form of learning in which knowledge, skills, abilities and habits of a group of people are transported from one generation to the next through teaching training, research or simply through auto-dictatism. India leads the world in the number of children and the majority of them are girls. While the enrolment of girls in public education has increased substantially since independence In the present world, overall female participation in education at all levels is still below 50% (Miller, 2007). Education for the girls is one of the principles that track ways to promote social and economic development. According to EFA global observing report 2003-04, increasing the educational level of girls has an encouraging influence upon economic growth. Since 2002, United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) and the global community have been striving to attain the Dakar Education for All (EFA) goals. Taking into consideration the fact that education for girls and women is a crucial preference, the Darker Framework for Action contained a time-bound goal; Goal five is dedicated explicitly to gender parity and equality in education (Ouma, 2013).

Moreover, special attention had been paid to women and girls in other goals; for example, goal two stipulates that by 2015, all children, especially girls in difficult circumstances and those belonging to ethnic minorities will have access to complete free and compulsory primary education of good quality. To encourage participation of girls in education, parents are required to provide them adequate teaching and learning facilities, protect them against societal problems, prohibit child marriage, practices of female foeticide, female infanticide, and provide financial assistance clothing and proper nutrition (Ouma, 2013). The individuals need to formulate this viewpoint that girls should be sent to schools and acquire education. They should create a pleasant environment within the house to promote education and learning. Education is regarded as an investment, whose returns are valued throughout the lives of the individuals. Through education, people acquire information, awareness, skills and attitudes essential for sustainable economic growth and general development. In the academic field, whatever they learn, they make use of it throughout their lives.

Importance of women education

“If you educate a man you educate an individual, however, if you educate a woman you educate a whole family. Women empowered means mother India empowered”. PT. JAWAHARLAL NEHRU. Women education in India plays a very important role in the overall development of the country. It not only helps in the development of half of the human resources, but in improving the quality of life at home and outside.¹ If it is said that education is the key to all problems, then it won't be improper. Thinkers have given a number of definitions of education but out of these definitions, the most important definition is that which was put forth by M. Phule.¹

According to M. Phule, "Education is that which demonstrates the difference between what is good and what is evil". If we consider the above definition, we come to know that whatever revolutions that have taken place in our history, education is at the base of them.² Education means modification of behaviour in every aspect, such as mentality, outlook, attitude etc. Educated women not only tend to promote education of their girl children, but also can provide better guidance to all their children. Moreover educated women can also help in the reduction of infant mortality rate and growth of the population.

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Socio-demographic Characteristics

The demographic characteristics of the respondents included sex, occupation, age, religion, marital status, level of education. It was found that patriarchy played an important role in determining social structures and organizations in India. Men are the heads of their families and they take every decision. The people are also patrilineal. Male children inherit family wealth and property. On the death of a father his eldest son takes over the mantle of leadership of the household. It was evident from the data that female household heads were almost non-existent in the communities of the districts of india. The training of girls is toward to filling of subordinate roles. A few women were interviewed in the households visited. This was only because their husbands or senior sons were not home.

It is also important to note that girls in this part of the country are not treated the same as boys. They go through a different socialization process from boys. They are trained to take up the trade of their mothers and on how to handle their future husbands. Their future carriers are linked to the

¹ Importance of girl child education: empowering girls through education. (2015) Retrieved from www.oxfamindia.org

socialization they get from infancy. This is often more or less vocational training and even when girls get into school, men end up taking decisions for them as heads of the household (Fayorsey, 1995).²

Early marriage

Too often marriage is seen as a higher priority than education. The low value attached to girls' schooling means few other options are available to them.

Boys can be affected but most victims of child marriage are girls. It is estimated that every year 15 million girls are married before they turn 18. After their wedding they leave the education system and, because they have fewer educational skills, they and their families are more likely to live in poverty.

Eighty-five percent (85%) of the respondents were married and 15% had experienced some form of marriage; divorced, widowed and/or separated. The study revealed that the people cherished marriage to the extent that some withdraw their daughters for school for the purposes of marriage. The study revealed that some girls in the district get married and continue their education and depending on the family in which the girl is coming from, they might marry as early as 16 years, this long before the legal age of 18 years. It can therefore be said that parents in the district now allow their daughters to marry at will and there is no specific age for marriage whether early or late marriage.

Pregnancy

One million girls under 15 give birth each year. In many parts of the world, girls who are pregnant - regardless of their circumstances - will be excluded from school.

Many do not return after giving birth due to those rules, stigma, fees, lack of childcare and the unavailability of flexible school programmes.

About 16 million girls aged 15 to 19 and some one million girls under 15 give birth every year—most in low- and middle-income countries, according to the World Health Organization.³

Level of Parents Education

There is a strong relationship between the level of parents' education and the number of girls in school. The positive relationship indicates that the higher the level of parental education, the higher the number of their girls in school. Level of parental education also determines the success rates of girl-child education in the Districts of India. Once the parents are educated, they make sure that their girls acquire the necessary educational qualifications in and for the future. The coefficient determination showed that only 93% of the variation between level of parental education and the number of children in school could be explained. The rest, seven percent (7%), of the variation could not be explained by the data. This finding is supported by a study conducted by Stuart (1981), which revealed that in Jordan, the level of education attained by fathers was systematically associated with the schooling of daughters thus establishing a positive relationship between fathers' and daughters'

² UNO (2000). The Girl Child. U.N. Department of Public Information. Accra.

³ <https://reliefweb.int/report/world/13-reasons-why-girls-are-not-school-international-day-girl-child>

education.⁴

Religious - Although in general performing in an indirect manner, the religious factor is on balance is a positive one, though it is often overcome by the fundamental socio-cultural prejudice in support of males. The fact, most religious specialists and leaders are males and this makes for an authoritative image in favour of boys, and it would be a co-operative move, if religious leaders of all trusts, beliefs and denominations were to speak out powerfully in support of the female cause.

Political/Administrative - Although policies exist in most cases for the developments in education, as universal primary education, equal educational opportunities in terms of gender and the elimination of gender bias from texts and other materials. The political will to carry these, though seems to be weak in the face of severe economic constraints. In the present existence, there has been formulation of laws and policies that girls should be regarded as equal; they should be encouraged towards acquisition of education and be given equal rights and opportunities. There should not be any type of discrimination between girls and boys and they should be equally considered with regards to employment opportunities, pay, enrolment in educational institutions and so forth.

Violence at school

Not only is this a violation of their human rights, it is also one of the most common causes for girls to drop out of school. An estimated 246 million girls and boys are harassed and abused on their way to and at school every year - with girls particularly vulnerable. 18 million girls aged 15 to 19 are victims of sexual violence - often leading to school dropout and reinforcing cultural practices such as early marriage.

Lack of funding

Too many girls are being left behind because funding is targeted to boys' education. Funding is an important issue when looking at reasons why girls aren't in school. Education for girls is often the lowest budget priority in many countries.

Daughters are perceived to be less valuable once educated, and less likely to abide by the will of the father, brother or husband. Often male siblings will be given the chance to attend school instead.

But educating girls and young women increases a country's productivity and contributes to economic growth. Some countries lose more than \$1 billion a year by failing to educate girls to the same level as boys.

Child/domestic labour

Millions of girls spend every day working to help feed themselves and their families. Girls often stay home to take care of younger siblings and bear the main burden of housework. While educating a boy is considered a sound investment, it is sometimes considered to be a waste of time for girls.

⁴ Amalu, C. (2003). 'The Problem of Girl Education. ' United Nation Children Fund (UNICEF) Ghana (unpublished report).

Many girls begin working as early as five years old - mainly in agriculture or in homes as domestic servants. Child domestic workers are particularly vulnerable to trafficking, forced labour, sexual violence and many health issues.

There are more than 168 million child labourers - 11% of all children in the world - who are working instead of learning. There are significantly more girls than boys working in service industries.

Natural disasters

Unforeseen events such as earthquakes, floods and disease can derail education for millions of girls. In humanitarian emergencies, including natural disasters, increased poverty for families and lack of employment opportunities means girls are at higher risk of early marriage or ending up in prostitution. Even if schools are still standing, families whose livelihoods have been destroyed may no longer be able to afford to send their daughters to school.

Because they are girls

Often, girls are marginalised and are out of school simply because they are girls and it is not the cultural norm. Their chances of getting a quality education are even smaller if they come from a poor family, live in a rural area or have a disability.

Girls are four times more likely to be out of school than boys from the same background. The poorest girls also have the least likelihood of completing primary school.

There are often legal, religious and traditional practices that discriminate against girls having the chance to get an education.

Female Foeticide and Female Infanticide

Female foeticide means the abortion of the female baby in the mother's womb. Whereas female infanticide is homicide of a baby girl after she has been born. The practice of homicide of the female child after her birth has been prevalent within the Indian society for many years. But foeticide is the inheritance and contribution of the advancement made by the medical science. Amniocentesis was introduced in 1975 to detect foetal abnormalities, but it soon began to be utilized for finding out the gender of the baby. Ultrasound scanning, being a non-invasive technique, rapidly acquired approval and is now available in some of the most inaccessible rural areas. Both techniques are now being used for sex determination with the meaning of abortion, if the foetus turns out to be female (Jena, 2008).

With the beginning of transfer and commercialization, the use of pre-natal diagnostic technologies is developing into a thriving corporate in India. This is principally for the determination of gender selective abortion of the female foetus. The mismanagement of technology, mainly puts emphasis upon the secondary status given to the girl children, in such a way that they are discarded out even before they are born. Associated to infanticide, foeticide is perhaps a more satisfactory means of positioning off the undesired girl children. Infanticide can be an obviously unpleasant and inhuman practice, while foeticide that is carried out by skilled professionals is a medical practice that makes use of scientific techniques and skills and decreases the responsibility factor that is connected with the complete implementation (Jena, 2008).

Why is the education of the girl child important?

In our country, many people are unaware of how the education of the girl child can transform lives for the better. It is a sad state of affairs when people across socio-economic strata think that investing in a girl child's education is a waste of money. The fact that they would rather justify spending on their daughter's marriage expenses or dowry instead of their education is even more disheartening. Early education can be instrumental in shaping the society towards progress. When a girl is educated, she is empowered. She can make decisions for herself, raise the standard of living for her family and children, generate more employment options and reform the society as a whole. Therefore, a change in the mindset towards girl child education in India is the need of the hour. Every girl child must be treated equally with love and respect.

The government has been making persistent efforts to raise the status of the girl child in the society as well as incentivize her education through various schemes and programs. These have surely contributed to girls' education to an extent yet a lot more needs to be done for girls to be truly treated as equal to boys.⁵

Importance of educating a girl child in Indian Society

Education is an essential part of a living being, whether it is a boy or a girl. Education helps an individual to be smarter, to learn new things and to know about the facts around the world. Especially [Girl education in India](#) is the need of the hour. In terms of inhabitants, India is the second largest nation in the world but the rate of girl education in India is extremely low. Educating the girl child must be a necessity for the overall development of the country as women play an essential part in the all-around process of the country. Generally, in rural areas, where people rarely want to send their daughters to school, they think that education is not important for girls as they grow up and eventually get married and settle down. People think that girls should be stay at home mothers to help their family and nothing else. This mentality is completely wrong and since girl education can bring around a massive revolution in the society, as lack of women education weakens the potent part of the society. There are many NGO's that are serving for this problem, but the most trustworthy one is CARE India. With the launch of their program Girl's Education Programme (GEP) that focuses on improving the condition by which girls, especially in rural areas can access quality education. There are several advantages of developing female education in India, since education can play an important role in the development of the country.⁶

Promote gender equality- Gender equality continues to be a prevalent issue in today's society due to the persistent gap in terms of access to opportunities for women and men. Gender equality is a fundamental human right that every human being is entitled to regardless of their race, ethnicity, sexuality or religion. The role men and women play in the society are totally determined and as a result there is a gender gap.

Improve literacy rate- India's literacy rate continues to be below the global average. Many NGO's

⁵ <https://www.cry.org/blog/importance-of-girl-child-education-in-india/>

⁶ **IMPORTANCE OF GIRL CHILD EDUCATION IN INDIA** Kanchan Joshi*, Neeta Bora Sharma** Abstract The main purpose of this research paper is to understand th

have helped to make a slight difference in the literacy rate. NGO's like CARE India has impacted more than 1, 36,000 children (52% girls from the marginalized communities) and 9, 00,000 children (54% girls) directly and indirectly. When girls are educated they can focus on other things rather than getting married at a young age. They can serve the society in many ways by practicing the profession that they want. This can help to play an important role in the society.

Alter the regressive nature of the society- It is believed that girl education in India is not that important as they grow up to eventually be stay-at-home mothers. Due to the regressive nature of India's society, the development of girl education has been hampered to a large extent. The majority of India's population is rural, and the mind-set that the majority of these people grow up with makes it quite challenging to educate these people about the benefits of girl education.

Conclusion

Education plays a vital role in the socio-economic and political aspects of woman's development. Through the use of education, the world has become a better place to live in. There has been the formulation of several policies and plans to improve the literacy rate in the country. RTE has brought some positive changes in gender disparity in schooling. But it focuses more on primary level of schooling that is the major reasons for dropping out drastically after ending their basic education. NEP is considered to play a vital role to tackle this problem. For the faster development of females, we all must recognize the significance of education for girls.

Gender inequality is one of the biggest challenges today. This can be tackled by eradicating poverty, providing free and compulsory education to girls; proper counselling, parenting enlightenment, and enhancing their safety. To ensure the enrolment of girls in schools government should take proper measures to implement the policies on the ground level. The task of undisputable girl-child education should be given priority. Though, the increment can be seen in the literacy rate among girls since independence. It is because of the steps taken by the government for the development of the girl child. It is hard to imagine the development of a society where the condition of girls is poor. Girls make up a family that makes a society which further helps in nation-building. There are number of factors, such as, economic, social, familial, educational and cultural that leads to barriers within the course of acquisition of education. In some cases, these factors impose major effects, due to which girls do not obtain any opportunities to acquire education, while on the other; they impose minor effects, which may hinder their development of educational qualifications. It is essential to formulate measures that lead to promotion of education amongst girls. In order to motivate girls, it is important to arouse understanding amongst their parents that girls are not only meant to perform the household chores, but they should be educated and allowed access to empowerment opportunities.

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